

Proton and Higgs Boson Mass Values Derived via Riemann Z-Vacuum Model

Gunnar Björklund ¹⁾

I. ABSTRACT

Rest mass energies for both the proton and the Higgs boson are derived from a previously published vacuum state model based on the Riemann Z-function.

The calculated proton mass value is within 12 ppm of what has been experimentally verified. This is equal to a 7 ppm improvement relative to the historically important proton-electron ratio of $6\pi^5 \approx 1836.118$, which around 1950 was within the tolerance of measurement, but later found to be 18 ppm lower than the real value.

The rest mass values of the Higgs boson, calculated via different Riemann Z-equations from the proton's rest mass, are within the accuracy of measurement of this mass according to the Particle Data Group (2024). The number of vacuum states per color charge of the proton is found to be close to four. An energy value close to the Rydberg unit is resulting from one of the equations.

In summary, the results open up for further exploration of how vacuum state modeling via the Riemann Z-function can shed light on the relation between the proton and the elementary particles of the Standard Model.

¹⁾ az-research@bjoerklund.eu

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7656-8346>

II. PROTON MASS DERIVATION

As postulated in a previous paper [1], vacuum states exist in combinations of three integer-cube sums 2^{S-1} where $S = n_1^3 + n_2^3 + n_3^3$; $S > 0$. The term 2^{S-1} is then exponentially raised via the infinite sum of positive integer cubic numbers leading or Riemann $\zeta(-3) = 1/120$ [2]. The resulting *number of combined vacuum states* is $2^{\frac{S-1}{120}}$. This number is multiplied with an energy value E_0 , resulting in a second energy value E via the *Riemann Z- Expression*:

$$E = E_0 2^{\frac{S-1}{120}}; \quad (1)$$

After setting E_0 equal to the electron rest mass $E_e \approx 510.99895$ keV [3] and $n_1^3 + n_2^3 + n_3^3 = 11^3 + 4^3 + 3^3$, the result is summarized by the following equation:

$$E = 2E_p \approx E_e 2^{(11^3+4^3+3^3-1)/120} \approx 2*937.750 \text{ MeV}; \quad (2)$$

This value is 0.06% lower than twice the CODATA rest mass value of the proton [4]: $E_p \approx 938.272 089$ MeV.

Adding the mass energy sum $2E_e$ of an electron-positron pair to the right side of Eq. 2 gives the following result:

$$E = 2E_p \approx E_e (2^{(11^3+4^3+3^3-1)/120} + 2) \approx 2*938.261 \text{ MeV}; \quad (3)$$

Which is 12 ppm lower than twice the official rest mass value of the proton [4].

III. THE PROTON-ELECTRON MASS RATIO

In a paper in Physical Review 1951 [5] the ratio between the proton and electron mass values was reported to be $6\pi^5$, which at the time was within the accuracy of measurement.

$$E_p/E_e \approx 6\pi^5 \approx 1836.118; \quad (4)$$

This is 19 ppm lower than the proton-electron mass ratio: 1836.152 673 426 [4].

The resulting ratio between the proton and electron mass energy values from Eq. 3 is:

$$E_p/E_e \approx \frac{1}{2}(2^{(11^3+4^3+3^3-1)/120} + 2) \approx 1836.130; \quad (5)$$

This is 7 ppm closer to the measured value of the proton-electron mass ratio compared with the value $6\pi^5$ according to Eq. 4.

It can be noted here that the *integers two and three* are fundamental in the equation: The factor $1/120 = \text{Riemann } \zeta(-3)$. The sum of the three n- integers $11+4+3 = 18$ results in $2^{(11+4+3)} = 64^3$.

IV. HIGGS MASS DERIVATION

It is now assumed that E_0 in the *Riemann Z- Expression*, defined by Eq. 1, represents twice the rest mass energy value of the proton, or the mass of the protonium atom consisting of a proton-antiproton pair: $E_0 = 2E_P$.

The resulting E-value is then:

$$E = 2E_P 2^{\frac{S-1}{120}} ; \text{ Where } S = n_1^3 + n_2^3 + n_3^3 ; S > 0 ; \quad (6)$$

Setting $n_1 = 9$, $n_2 = -1$ and $n_3 = -1$, results in the following equation of the rest mass of the Higgs boson E_{Hgs} :

$$E \approx 2E_P 2^{(9^3-3)/120} \approx 2E_P 4.0465^3 \approx E_{Hgs} \approx 124.3341 \text{ GeV}; \quad (7)$$

It is here observed that $2^{(9^3-3)/120} = (2^{(6^3+3^3-1)/120})^3 \approx 4.05^3$. This *cubic Riemann expression* can be regarded as the combined number of vacuum states related to the three color charges (red, green and blue) of the proton, according to quantum chromodynamics, with 4.05 as the approximate number of vacuum states per color.

It is also possible to derive an approximate value of the Rydberg unit via the equation:

$$E \approx 4E_P / 2^{(15^3-2^3-1^3-1)/120} \approx 13.58 \text{ eV}; \quad (8)$$

This value is 0.16 % lower than the Rydberg unit of energy, $Ry \approx 13.60569 \text{ eV}$ [4], the negative value of which is equal to the ground state energy of the hydrogen atom.

Setting $n_1 = 9$, $n_2 = 0$ and $n_3 = -1$, results in the following approximate expression of the rest mass of the Higgs boson E_{Hgs} :

$$E \approx 2E_P 2^{(9^3-2)/120} \approx 2E_P 4.0542^3 \approx E_{Hgs} \approx 125.054 \text{ GeV}; \quad (9)$$

Another value of E_{Hgs} is resulting from having E_0 in Eq. 1 equal to the Higgs Vacuum Expectation Value: $VEV = E_H = 246.22 \text{ GeV}$ [6]:

$$E = E_H 2^{-(3^3+3^3+4^3-1)/120} \approx E_{Hgs} \approx 125.26 \text{ GeV}; \text{ See also ref. [1].} \quad (10)$$

This E-value has its precision determined by the accuracy of the E_H -value, which is depending on the tolerance of the rest mass value of the W-boson [3].

The E_{Hgs} -values from Eq. 7, Eq. 9 and Eq. 10 are within the mass energy range of the Higgs boson, according to PDG: $125.20 \pm 0.11 \text{ GeV}$ [3].

V. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

In the publication [1], vacuum state modeling derived from the Riemann Z function has resulted in mass energy values of the bosons and leptons of the Standard Model. The calculations were based on the VEV- and the Planck mass energies. These calculations, now extended to include the proton, are resulting in rest mass energy values for both the proton and the Higgs boson.

The E-value resulting from Eq. 3 is 12 ppm lower than the twice the rest mass value of the proton. This leads to a proton-electron mass energy ratio which is 7 ppm closer to the experimentally verified value than the historically important $6\pi^5 \approx 1836.118$.

The calculation of the Higgs boson mass from both the proton mass and the VEV is resulting in energy values which are within 0.2 GeV respectively 0.1 GeV from the PDG-value of 125.20 GeV. The mean value of these two calculated values of the Higgs boson mass is 125.16 GeV, which after being rounded off to one decimal place is identical with the PDG-value [3].

The calculation of E-values for the Higgs boson from the rest mass of the protonium shows that there are around 4.05 vacuum states per color.

It is concluded from the results above that the proton can have its rest mass meticulously derived, both from the rest mass of the electron and the Higgs boson; Also, by only a slight modification of one of these equations, a value close to the Rydberg unit of energy is derived from the proton's rest mass.

The Riemann Z-vacuum model is firmly relating energy values of the Higgs boson and the Higgs VEV to those of the electron and the proton, which together constitute the most abundant element of the universe, namely the hydrogen atom.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] G. Björklund. ResearchGate April 2023
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20390.60484> (10pp)
- [2] Roman Dworkin & Jan Minac. (2023). Values of the Riemann zeta function at integers.
- [3] R.L. Workman et al. Particle Data Group (PDG).
https://pdg.lbl.gov/2024/tables/contents_tables.html
- [4] CODATA Internationally recommended 2022-values of the Fundamental Physical Constants. <https://physics.nist.gov/cuu/Constants/index.html>
- [5] F. Lenz .Phys. Rev. 82, 554. 15 May 1951.
- [6] The Astrophysical Journal, 723:803–811, 2010 November 1. p.805.